

STANDARD TRANSFER METADATA FOR BORN-DIGITAL TRANSFERS

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Abstract - The poster will describe the Standard Transfer Metadata File (STMF) which is being developed at Archives New Zealand (Archives NZ). It comes in two forms: an XML schema definition (XSD) and detailed guidelines aimed at government agencies which transfer their born-digital records to Archives NZ. Archives NZ processed its first digital transfer in 2015, although they accepted urgent digital transfers before then. Since then, we have handled several transfers and learned that the variety and inconsistency in transferred metadata form and layout is a repeating issue, making the process difficult and slower both for the agencies and for the digital preservation team and transfer archivists at Archives NZ.

STMF is our answer to this, and the poster will present the standard, its structure, its metadata fields and the way we envision it helping to better facilitate born-digital transfers for agencies and Archives NZ. One of the goals of our poster will be to collect feedback from iPRES attendees on our standard proposal, as there are archives in many countries where a similar standard is already in place.

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I. BORN-DIGITAL TRANSFERS

Public Records Act 2005 [1] was a keenly anticipated change for Archives New Zealand (Archives NZ). It codified the need for transferring the records from government agencies to Archives NZ in any form, i.e. including digital. Urgent born-digital transfers were accepted from 2006 into the Interim

Digital Archive (IDA), which was mostly just storage. Digital transfer was not a standardised process and the level of digital preservation functionalities provided by IDA was very low.

Archives NZ ran a project called Government Digital Archive Programme (GDAP) from 2010-2013. It had two goals: to deliver a new digital archive system and the ability to accept and process born-digital transfers. GDAP was closed early and the ability to process digital transfers was never delivered. As for the digital archive, it was decided to use an already existing instance of the Rosetta preservation system at the National Library and to share that system and infrastructure. All content of the IDA was migrated to Archive NZ's part of Rosetta (Government Digital Archive) in 2011 and 2012.

II. INTERIM RESPONSE AND TRANSFER REQUIREMENTS

After the GDAP project was closed, Archives NZ had to find a way how to establish the ability to accept and process digital transfers. It was decided to build a minimal requirement workflow referred to as the Interim Response. The result was a set of Python scripts, guidelines, requirements and a workflow which have been used by Archives NZ ever since. The first official transfer via this framework was processed in 2015.

The requirements published for the agencies were not extensive, but gradually we realised that some agencies were put off by them. We simplified the requirements over time only to end up with the bare minimum.

We require public agencies to export the metadata from their system in any way and form, namely all the metadata fields, and transfer it to us ideally as a spreadsheet. Similarly for files, we don't prescribe any file format for the transfer, and we stress that we don't want the agency to migrate their records to any format for the sake of the transfer. To process the transfer, we need required descriptive metadata as per recordkeeping standards, a checksum value for each file, the file name and full file path in the metadata sheet.

III. EVERY TRANSFER IS A PROJECT

With these simple requirements we were able to get agencies to transfer to Archives NZ. But over the years we have realised that with the lack of a transfer standard, each transfer is treated as a project of its own.

For each transfer we must analyse the descriptive metadata with our transfer archivists, as the metadata associated with each transfer is unique to that agency. Not only because the metadata is exported from a different system, but because there are inconsistencies between the metadata field names and between the metadata provided. For example, a record creator may be called "Creator" in one agency and be called "Author" in another. The record name might be "Title" or "Name", etc. Because of this, we must do metadata mapping for each transfer, often even for transfers coming from the same EDRM system but from different agencies. To process transfers like this requires a lot of back-and-forth discussion between transfer archivists and agencies and it also relies on a certain technical threshold. For instance, does the agency initially know how to export the metadata from their EDRMS,

Handling the metadata in a spreadsheet brings another set of problems, from coding and character sets used, to unwanted changes made by Microsoft Excel.

There is also the digital preservation aspect. We carefully analyse the files in each transfer, but this analysis process is out of scope for this submission.

IV. STANDARD TRANSFER METADATA FILE (STMF)

To address all the issues with inconsistent metadata we came up with the idea of prescribing exactly how the metadata for born-digital transfer

should look. A similar approach and related standards are common in many countries already.

Having a standard in the form of a published metadata schema (XSD) and as a detailed set of guidelines would streamline the whole process. Agencies can use the XSD in their EDRM systems to enable the exporting of metadata as XML in the correct form, directly from their system and subsequently create a batch of data and metadata for transfer. We plan to talk to EDRMS vendors, so that they can explore implementing STMF within their products as one of the export options. Some EDRM systems used in New Zealand offer NAA (National Archives of Australia), NARA (National Archives, U.S.) and VEO (Victoria, Australia) export options already.

From the Archives NZ process point of view, we won't need to map agency metadata to our own metadata schema for each transfer. We will have one mapping between STMF and our descriptive system metadata which will be applied to each transfer.

We plan to provide support tools such as an STMF XML validator so that the agency can validate and confirm all the mandatory fields are present in their export and in required form and layout.

V. STMF STRUCTURE

The Standard Transfer Metadata XML file has three main parts. Firstly, a header which contains details about the actual transfer such as agency code and transfer ID.

Second and most importantly, the actual metadata for transferred records (items) with descriptive metadata for the records, and technical and provenance metadata for transferred files. STMF is designed to support hybrid transfers, i.e. the record/item can be physical or digital; or just a descriptive item without any actual physical or digital records attached to it. Examples of technical metadata for digital files are "size", "filePath", "fileName", "dateCreated", "checksum", "creatingApplication". A majority of the fields is optional as we are aware that government agencies do not usually create and keep technical details about the records.

The third part of STMF is "Relationships", where the relationship between records can be described. This is important for keeping the original record

structure and for providing access in a way which resembles the original record context.

VI. CONCLUSION

Standard Transfer Metadata File is being developed to address inconsistencies in metadata in born-digital transfers. By specifying clearly what metadata fields are required, like the form and layout in which they should be created, we can make the born-digital transfer process easier. It will be easier for agencies to prepare the metadata for transfer, and it will be more streamlined for archivists to process it. STMF will be published for public feedback in late 2025.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Public Record Act 2005 No 40". New Zealand Legislation.
<https://www.legislation.govt.nz/act/public/2005/0040/latest/DLM345529.html> (accessed April 3, 2025)

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Jan Hutař is a Digital Preservation Analyst at Archives New Zealand. He holds a PhD in Information Science, an MA in Information Studies and Librarianship and a BA in Archival Studies. Jan is responsible for developing digital preservation policies and processes, digital preservation system management and providing advice to government agencies regarding born-digital record transfer.

